

TNIKA Purification undertaken by Mira Rothweiler:

TNIKA-c385

MIFELVELVGNNGTYGQVYKGRHVKTGQLAAIKVMDVTGDEEEEEIKQEINMLKKYSHHRNIATYYGAFIKKNPPGM
DDQLWLVMFEFCGAGSVTDLIKNTKGNTLKEEWIAYICREILRGLSHLHQHKVIHRDIKGQNVLLTENA EVKLVD
VSAQLDRTVGRNRTFIGTPYWMapeviacdenpdatydfksdlwslgitaieMaegapPLCDMHPMRALFLIPR
NPAPRLKSKKWSKKFQSFIESCLVKNHSQRPATEQLMKHPFIRDQPNERQVRIQLKDHIDRTKKKRGKDETEYEA
HHHHHH

Expression:

1. Inoculate all of overnight culture (20 ml) with 2 L TB + Phos + Kan)
2. Grow in 37 degree shaker until log phase (250 rpm)
3. Check cells for log phase growth until OD (600) ~ 2.0.
4. Add 1ml IPTG to induce expression.
5. Grow overnight in 18 °C shaker
6. Store pellets at -20 °C

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate for 3 min (35 on, 6 off) on ice.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (aprox 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 1 hour.
- Incubate lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 30 min. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Add 1mM TCEP to all fractions.
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

SDS-PAGE gel of TNIKA purification by Nickle affinity.

- Concentrate fractions E1, E4/1 and E4/2 samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 200 column using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.

TNIKA SDS PAGE gel shows samples from the relevant size exclusion column fractions, corresponding to the UV peak shown in the top panel.

- Pool fractions back together and concentrate down before flash freezing in liquid nitrogen.

Tm shift of M4K Pharma compounds with TNIK

Four compound plates used: K115, K116, K117 and K118. Both plates contain compounds from M4K Pharma and other related collaborators as well as K02288 as a positive control.

Make up protein solution to 2uM protein in 10mM Hepes, 50mM HEPES pH7.5

Add 1:1000 dilution of Sypro orange to 2.2ml of protein solution

Pipette 0.5ul of compound into the bottom of a 96 well PCR plate.

Pipette 19.5ul of protein into the wells.

Seal with optically active plate seals.

Spin down for 1 minute.

Run a thermal scan on an RT-PCR machine cycling from 21°C to 95°C over the course of 24 minutes.

Analyse results using excel and graph pad prism to integrate curves to find the midpoint and thus the Tm shift. DMSO only and Water controls embedded in the plate used to calculate reference cells from which to base the Tm shift from.

A comparison of ALK2 vs. TNIK shows many compounds appear to be selective for ALK2 including M4K2009 which gives a 14.1 °C shift for ALK2 but only 1.8 °C for TNIK.

K115 (1) w TNIK

K115 (2) w TNiK

K116 (1) w/ TNIK

K116 (2) w/ TNIKA

K117 (1) w/ TNIKA

K117 (2) w/ TNIKA

K118 (1) w/ TNIKA

K118 (2) w/ TNIKA

Phosphomapping of TNIKA

TNIKA was incubated at different concentrations (1mM, 10mM, 20mM, 30mM, 40mM, 50mM) with 50mM SMAD1 in the presence of 5mM DTT, 2mM Mn, 5mM Mg, 5mM ATP and samples were taken at regular intervals over 2 hours at 5, 10, 30, 60 and 120 minutes.

Samples were quenched in water with 0.1% formic acid and intact mass spec was run using a QTOF mass spectrometer. A C3 cartridge was used for HPLC prior to ionisation.

The resulting chromatogram was used to extract the appropriate spectra corresponding to protein elution peak from the C3 column. All spectra were extracted simultaneously. Deconvolution was undertaken between 10kDa and 50kDa across a limited m/z range of 600 – 3000.

Data was exported with a peak intensity for every Dalton of the deconvoluted spectra and graphs were plotted in excel as seen in the uploaded file 'timecourse_plotting.xlsx'. This confirmed that a single phosphorylation event was observed on SMAD after 10 minutes at multiple concentrations of TNIK.

Phosphorylation mapping was then undertaken using MS/MS analysis. MS/MS data collection was undertaken by Dr. Rod Chalk. 5 different cleavage enzymes were used both unenriched and enriched for phosphopeptides using TiO₂/ZrO affinity columns, in order to get sufficient coverage to see all likely phosphorylation sites.

Data analysis was done on the mascot website using a custom database containing the sequences of the components of the reaction, i.e. SMAD1 and TNIK only. A peptide score of 23 was used as a cut off to identify peptides with high confidence. Phosphopeptides were then identified through observations of consecutive ions present, the presence of neutral loss, whether there was any site ambiguity and how varied the error was on the ions.

From this a number of different phosphopeptides were detected that could be mapped onto the sequence as either confirmed or ambiguous, and the overall total coverage of the proteins could be determined.

A full table of all the phosphopeptides can be found in the document 'Phosphomapping_v2.xlsx' while below is a summary of the peptide coverage and the identified phosphorylation sites.

SMAD1-c001

SMAPPLPSEI NRGDVQAVAY EEPKHWCSIV YYELNNRVGE AFHASSTSVL
VDGFTDPSNN KNRFCGLGLS NVNRNSTIEN TRRHIGKGVH LYYVGGEVYA
ECLSDSSIFV QSRNCNYHHG FHPTTVCKIP SGCSLKIFNN QEFAQLLAQS
VNHGFETVYE LTKMCTIRMS FVKGWGAEYH RQDVTSTPCW IEIHLHGPLQ
WLDKVLTMG SPHNPISSVS

TNIKA-c385

MIFELVELVG NGTYGQVYKG RHVKTGQLAA IKVMDVTGDE EEEIKQEINM
LKKYSHHRNI ATYYGAFIKK NPPGMDDQLW LVMEFCGAGS VTDLIKNTKG
NTLKEEWIAY ICREILRGLS HLHQHKVIHR DIKGQNVLLT ENAEVKLVDF
GVSAQLDRTV GRRNTFIGTP YWMAPEVIAC DENPDATYDF KSDLWSLGIT
AIEMAEGAPP LCDMHPMRAL FLIPRNPAPR LKSKKWSKKF QSFIESCLVK
NHSQRPATEQ LMKHPFIRDQ PNERQVRIQL KDHDRTKCK RGEKDETEYE
AHHHHHH

BLUE = Definitive Phosphorylation

ORANGE = Ambiguous Phosphorylation

RED = Peptide coverage

Summary of identified peptides showing overall coverage (red), definitive phosphorylation (blue) and ambiguous phosphorylation (orange).

A number of sites were identified on TNIK which must be due to auto-phosphorylation. Three sites were identified on SMAD1 definitively and a further three ambiguously.

- Three of these sites (one firm and two ambiguous - PI**SSVS**) are known sites of phosphorylation by ALK2 however we know that ALK2 cannot phosphorylate them alone and requires a type II receptor for this to happen – it seems that under in-vitro conditions TNIK is not under the same restriction.
- One of these sites (FE**T**VY) is not known to be involved in SMAD1 inhibition but it cannot be ruled out yet and may bear further investigation
- Two of these sites (one firm and one ambiguous – RN**ST**IE) are in the location suggested by Wang et. al. (2016) as being the consensus sequence for TNIK phosphorylation of SMAD1.